

Status of Collusive Bidding in World Bank Funded Road Projects of Nepal

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ABSTRACT:

The comparative bidding is assumed to be implemented through public procurement for infrastructure projects. The case study of world bank funded projects has been conducted as extension of earlier study to assure the current status of collusive bidding in road projects using bidding data, contract data, focus group discussion as effective data collection tools from Bid Evaluation Reports, DTOs, World Bank Country Office for Descriptive, qualitative and quantitative analysis to know the status of collusive trend of bidding in two different environment.

The Collusive trending in conventional bidding system is reasonably high with 47% while the number sharply declines with 13% of the total sampled bid. It is revealed that 25% of winning bid is in the range of 0-5% below the Engineers' Estimate in conventional bidding system while it is only 13.85% in E-bidding. The ratio of bidders purchasing the bid documents and submission is considerably reduced after the launching of e-bidding system. The environment of construction business has been improved with consistent bidding pattern as revealed in the E-bidding system. Conventional ways of rate analysis uses the district rate and GoN Norms (DOR, DOLIDAR) which are based on labour intensive technology and this doesn't match with mechanized work system. Norms developed by concerning departments are not compatible with the desired specifications of clients.

Keywords: bid submission, public procurement, e-bidding, status, ratio etc.

Background

Collusive Bidding

In various literatures, collusive tendering or collusive bidding or bid rigging or cartel on bidding is explained synonymously. The main form of collusion is bid rigging behavior; the collusion in the public procurement market is a relationship among bidders which restricts competition and harms the public procurement. As per (OECD, n.d.), Bid rigging (or collusive tendering) occurs when businesses, that would otherwise be expected to compete, secretly conspire to raise prices or lower the quality of goods or services for purchasers who wish to acquire products or services through a bidding process. (Bista, 2015)

Porter & Zona (1992) says about cartel...." a cartel might adopt a pure bid rotation scheme, where members take turns submitting bids in individual auctions (according to a "phases of the moon" scheme, for example). Alternatively, cartel members in addition to the designated winner may submit higher complementary or frivolous bids, perhaps to create the appearance of competition".

According to Zarkada-Fraser & Skitmore (1998) collusive tendering is defined as an explicit

agreement between [competitors] either not to tender, or to tender in such a manner as not to be competitive with one of the other tenderers". Between 1982 and 1988, more than half of the criminal cases filed by the Antitrust Division of the Department of Justice involved bid rigging or price fixing in auction markets. Bid rigging appears to be a pervasive problem, with indictments in highway construction, the distribution of school milk, utility procurement and other auction markets. Typically, a government agency, and hence the taxpayer, was the victim (Porter & Zona, 1992).

Suntharanurak (2012) describe in his Ph.D. dissertation "In fact, the main form of collusion is bid rigging behavior. Bid rigging is firstly a competition law violation in which bidders illegally agree on a price for goods and services or agree not to bid in a tender. Through the bid rigging behavior, the government will pay artificially high prices for goods or services. It affects not only the national level, but also the international level (Chowdury, 2008: 2). The impact of collusive bidding at the international level involves domestic cartels attempting to preserve a narrow domestic procurement market by obstructing foreign firms from participating in bidding in the domestic market. For example, during 1990s the construction cartel in Japan known as Dango obstructed construction firms from the US to compete in the tendering of a new international airport project in Japan. Finally, the US government pressured the Japanese government to eliminate the Dango behavior in order to encourage fair competition. (Woodall, 1996: 19) Likewise, Maci (2011) described the context of collusive bidding occurring in EU procurement markets. This restrictive practice contradicts the goal of EU public procurement policy which is aimed at integrating these markets in order to allow public procurers to obtain the benefits of the common market. (Bista, 2015)

Initially, bid rigging is a particular form of collusive price-fixing behavior by which firms coordinate their bids on procurement or project contracts. Also bid rigging is one of the most widely prosecuted forms of collusion. The Antitrust Division of United States Department of Justice explained that bid rigging is the way in which conspiring competitors effectively raise prices where purchasers such as federal, state or local government acquire goods and services by soliciting competing bids. Likewise, the (OECD, n.d.) clarified that a bid rigging often occurs in the construction industry when bidders agree among themselves to eliminate competition in the procurement process. Under bid rigging behavior, the government always pays for goods and services above the market price. Thus, bid rigging has a direct impact on public expenditure and consequently on taxpayers' resources.

In Japan, bid rigging is regulated by Antimonopoly Act of 1947. In article 2.6 of this law, it defined bid rigging behavior as the restriction of business activities through mutual cooperation between companies and substantial restraint of competition in certain business areas against public interests."

In (Competition Commission of India, n.d.) describe collusive bidding or bid rigging may occur in various ways. Some of the most commonly adopted ways are:

- i. agreements to submit identical bids
- ii. agreements as to who shall submit the lowest bid, agreements for the submission

- of cover bids (voluntarily inflated bids)
- iii. agreements not to bid against each other,
 - iv. agreements on common norms to calculate prices or terms of bids
 - v. agreements to squeeze out outside bidders
 - vi. agreements designating bid winners in advance on a rotational basis, or on a geographical or customer allocation basis
 - vii. agreement as to the bids which any of the parties may offer at an auction for the sale of goods or any agreement through which any party agrees to abstain from bidding for any auction for the sale of goods, which eliminates or distorts competition

Furthermore, (CUTS International, 2008, n.d.) define "Bid rigging is a form of collusion, i.e. a cartelized anti-competitive practice which results in costs that are in excess of justifiable levels". Most common forms of bid rigging are described as:

Sub-contract Bid Rigging: Where some of the bidders opt out of the process under the agreement that some parts of the bid will be sub-contracted to them.

Complementary Bidding: Where some of the bidders submit bids which are either too high or contain unacceptable conditions, defrauding purchasers in the process by creating the appearance of genuine competitive bidding.

Bid Rotation: Where the bidders take turns winning the bid.

Bid Suppression: Where some of the bidders opt out of the bid so that the designated winning competitor's bid will be accepted.

Market Division: Where competing firms allocate specific customers or types of customers, products, or territories among themselves and the winning bid is decided in accordance with such allocation.

Common Bidding: Where firms agree to submit common bids, thus eliminating price competition.

(Fair Trading Commission, Barbados, n.d.)describes the method of detecting bid rigging in public procurement as follows:

- i. Warning Signs when Bids are Submitted
- ii. Warning Signs in Documents Submitted
- iii. Signs Related to Pricing: loosing bids are much higher than the winners' bid, bid price that are higher than engineering cost estimates etc.
- iv. Suspicious Statements
- v. Suspicious Behaviors

(Suntharanurak, 2012) described about detection of bid rigging in public procurement as:

Detecting when bids are submitted: In concentrated markets it seems to be easy for the firm which could organize the ring to be the winner. For example, the same bidders may always win bids of a certain type or size; meanwhile another bidder never wins but still keeps bidding. Likewise, the bid pattern may show one firm that consistently wins bids but always subcontracts to smaller firms refrains unexpectedly for no reason. (Bista, 2015)

Detecting from documents submitted: Initially, the documentation may also be a clear indicator of collusion among firms. For example, firms may employ the same personnel to create the bidding document. This creates visible errors in the documents where they may use the same type of paper, the same misspelling, handwriting, wording, calculations. In order to use this detecting method, officials must scrutinize all documentation thoroughly (Bista, 2015).

Detecting from pricing or pricing related signals: It is important to look for price increases that cannot be explained by cost increases. We might be aware of the market trends with respect to input cost, such as changes in raw material costs or variances in oil prices which will push the final prices of the bidder. Though cost might not affect the bidding price, the bidding ring might set up that the losing firm's bids are much higher than the designated winner in complementary bidding. In addition, another warning sign of bid rigging is that the bidding price might be higher than the engineering cost estimates, or higher than prior bids for similar tenders may also indicate collusion (Mishra and Shing, 2019).

Furthermore, (Suntharanurak, 2012) describe the collusive bidding behavior as "under the collusive bidding, each contractor could agree before bidding. Thus, in order to maximize profit the strategy of bidding ring is to designate winner firm before the auction. The winning bid in this case will come close to the engineers' estimated cost. The designate winner does not need to concern other bidders in the ring to compete for the bidding ring will allocate the benefit to all members in the ring through the side payment, the subcontract or rotating a winner for the next project. However, the bidding ring will not set the designated winning bid equal to the engineers' estimated cost since it might show an unusual bidding. The designated winner in general will submit a bid price closely to the engineers' estimated cost.

Screening for bid rigging by using engineers' estimated cost is based on the study of Visuth Chorvichien et al. (2002: 4-6) who reported that any public procurement with a difference between engineers' estimate cost and a winning bid price less than 5 percent could signal a bid rigging. The conclusion came from interviews of 48 experienced contractors in the public works construction market of Thailand. Actually, the study of Visuth Chorvichien et al.(2002) still coincided with the screening method of (Welsch & Furth, 1983), who suggested the bid rigging analysis for investigator, auditor and attorney in US. They found that the initial screening method consisted of the reviewing all bid tabs and selecting those projects from five or fewer bidders which the lowest bid price was within 5 percent of the state engineer's estimate."

Impact of Collusive Bidding

The effect of collusive bidding is that it discourages genuine price competition through which a huge sum of public money could have been saved and used in other sectors. Collusive bidding can create several disputes and claims and it result in schedule delays and increase in project costs. The monopoly in construction business restricts from competing for quality and promotes certain group of firms only and restricts the entry of new firms who could not cartel for a job regularly.

Assessments of public procurement reform in developing countries

Transparent procurement procedures can contribute to a more efficient allocation of resources through increased competition, higher quality procurement and budgetary savings for governments and thus for taxpayers. They can also help attract more investment by lowering risk. Objective and transparent procedures can in addition help enhance the efficiency of local suppliers as they compete for public contracts, thereby improving trade prospects by making these suppliers more competitive exporters.... Finally, transparent procurement procedures can help limit bribery and corruption, which are particularly rampant in the procurement field” (OECD 2003).

Box 1. Examples of cost-savings under transparent procurement systems

- Through the strengthening of transparency and procurement procedures including, for example, eliminating any tender specifications that favor a particular tender, Guatemala’s Ministry of Health reports savings of 43 percent on the purchase of medicines.
- The Colombian Ministry of Defense reports generating 47 percent savings in the procurement of military goods through improvement of transparency and procurement procedures.
- Nicaragua had been spending about 17 percent of its health budget on pharmaceuticals. High drug expenditure had resulted from a lack of pricing and drug information and non-transparent procurement procedures. With the establishment of a transparent procurement agency, accompanied by the effective implementation of an essential drug list, the government was able to reduce drug costs significantly. Within one year of introducing these measures, the government had reduced its pharmaceutical budget from \$21 million in 1992 to \$13 million in 1993.
- In Pakistan, an open and transparent bidding process has resulted in savings of more than Rs 187 million (US \$3.1m) for the Karachi Water and Sewerage Board.
- After introducing transparent procurement procedures in the energy sector, Bangladesh was able to reduce electricity prices to less than US \$0.03 a Kilo Watt-hour, roughly half the price of directly negotiated deals in Indonesia.

Source: OECD (2003).

Principles of Competitive Bidding

Competitive bidding on construction projects involves decision making under uncertainty where one of the greatest sources of the uncertainty for each bidder is due to the unpredictable nature of his competitors. Each bid submitted for a particular job by a contractor will be determined by a large number of factors, including an estimate of the direct job cost, the general overhead, the confidence that the management has in this estimate, and the immediate and long-range objectives of management. So many factors are involved that it is impossible for a particular bidder to attempt to predict exactly what the bids submitted by its competitors will be.

It is useful to think of a bid as being made up of two basic elements: (1) the estimate of direct job cost, which includes direct labor costs, material costs, equipment costs, and direct field supervision; and (2) the markup or return, which must be sufficient to cover a portion of general overhead costs and allow a fair profit on the investment. A large return can be assured simply by including a sufficiently high markup. However, the higher the markup, the less chance there will be of getting the job. Consequently a contractor who includes a very large markup on every bid could become bankrupt from lack of business. Conversely, the strategy of bidding with very little markup in order to obtain high volume is also likely to lead to bankruptcy. Somewhere in between the two extreme approaches to bidding lies an "optimum markup" which considers both the return and the likelihood of being low bidder in such a way that, over the long run, the average return is maximized.

From all indications, most contractors confront uncertain bidding conditions by exercising a high degree of subjective judgment, and each contractor may give different weights to various factors. The decision on the bid price, if a bid is indeed submitted, reflects the contractor's best judgment on how well the proposed project fits into the overall strategy for the survival and growth of the company, as well as the contractor's propensity to risk greater profit versus the chance of not getting a contract (Construction_pricing_and_contracting.html).

Characteristics of Bidding Competition

All other things being equal, the probability of winning a contract diminishes as more bidders participate in the competition. Consequently, a contractor tries to find out as much information as possible about the number and identities of potential bidders on a specific project (Construction_pricing_and_contracting.html).

Objectives of General Contractors in Bidding

The bidding strategies of some contractors are influenced by a policy of minimum percentage markup for general overhead and profit. However, the percentage markup may also reflect additional factors stipulated by the owner such as high retention and slow payments for completed work, or perceptions of uncontrollable factors in the economy. The intensity of a contractor's efforts in bidding a specific project is influenced by the contractor's desire to obtain additional work. The winning of a particular project may be potentially important to the overall mix of work in progress or the cash flow implications for the contractor. The contractor's decision is also influenced by the availability of key personnel in the contractor

organization. The company sometimes wants to reserve its resources for future projects, or commits itself to the current opportunity for different reasons (Construction_pricing_and_contracting.html).

Construction Industry

The construction industry represents a large segment of the total economy. Over a million, companies ranging in size and specialty make the construction industry one of the largest of all industries. Businesses in the construction industry interact with businesses in related industries that supply materials, equipment, financing, and bonding to the construction contractor. Each business is dependent on one another for their survival (Construction industry).

Construction Industry in Nepal

The history of construction contract is relatively new in Nepal. Since a long time the government has remained the main investor for most of the public construction works. Due to the small size of economy and investment capacity, there had been small and simple type of construction projects in Nepal in the past. During that early period no professional constructor equipped with modern managerial skills, management tools and techniques had emerged in Nepal. (World Bank, Research Paper)

In 1955 Nepal became the member of the United Nation, and gradually developed relationship with other nations. It started receiving financial and technical assistance from bilateral and multi-lateral agencies for the development of public works infrastructure in the country. This increased construction activity in the country. During this period, the donor countries executed projects involving their own technical manpower and using Nepalese people only as unskilled and semi skilled workers. The government-funded projects too had been undertaken directly on labour basis without formal contracting (i.e. there was no contractual provision of any kind). Such practices in the long led to people however getting some skills of construction works. This gradually but steadily developed the capacity of foremen and skilled workers involved in such projects, which ultimately lead to the development of small work force in the country capable of under taking responsibility for small works through contract. (World Bank, Research Paper)

After 1970 AD, due to the ambitious national development plan of the government a large number of different capital-intensive construction projects were initiated. In the mean time, the government has come to realize the necessity for professional contractors in undertaking the responsibility of such large-scale construction works.

The government enacted a rule: contractor-related rules, 2031 BS. This was the first milestone, which recognized the contractor as a professional and the construction activity as a business in the history of construction industry in Nepal. As per this rules the Contractor should obtain classification certificate to be eligible for entering into construction contracts.

Afterwards, the number of registered contractors increased tremendously. The government gradually made its fiscal rules and regulations conducive for promotion of construction contracts.

Research Objectives

The objective of this research is to assess the Status of Collusive Bidding in World Bank Funded Road Projects of Nepal.

Methodology

Methodology adopted

To conduct the research for “the Status of Collusive Bidding in World Bank Funded Road Projects of Nepal., the following methodology has been adopted from Mishra and Singh , 2019 as it is an extension of the same study.

Figure 1 Structure of Methodology

Methods of Data Collection

Table 1 Data Analysis Outline

S.N.	Description	Bids Received in Conventional Bidding System	Bids received in E-bidding system
1	Bids purchase and submission pattern	Data of 45 sampled contracts	Data of 45 sampled contracts
2	Overall Trend Analysis Pattern Specific parameters for paved road contracts Specific parameter for unpaved road contracts.	Data of 45 sampled contracts	Data of 45 sampled contracts
3	Bids Assessment Against Threshold Values- Normal Bids, Low Bids	Data of 45 sampled contracts	Data of 45 sampled contracts
4	Questionnaire Survey among clients and contractors: responses of respondents are analyzed		

The screening and interpretation of collusive bidding study will use the difference between the engineers' estimated cost and the winning bid price as a tool. Public procurement with a difference between engineers' estimate cost and a winning bid price less than 5 percent are assumed as collusive bids. The research findings also suggest that number of bids less than or equal to 3 for construction in normal circumstances are assumed as collusive trend of bidding. Researcher assumes these two criteria only to detect collusive bidding, even though there are various characteristics of collusive bidding in public procurement.

Table 2. Summary of Methodology

SN	Objectives	Tools for Data Collection	Data Source	Analysis method	Expected outcome
1	to study the current status of collusive bidding in road projects	bidding data, contract data, focus group discussion	Bid Evaluation Reports, DTOs, World Bank Country Office	Descriptive, qualitative and quantitative analysis	know the status of collusive trend of bidding in two different environment

Status of Collusive Bidding

Literature Review suggests the findings of screening method of (Welsch & Furth, 1983) who suggested the bid rigging analysis for investigator, auditor and attorney in US for analysis of

collusive nature of tendering in construction business. They found that the initial screening method consisted of the reviewing all bid tabs and selecting those projects from five or fewer bidders which the lowest bid price was within 5 percent of the Engineer’s Estimate. As per this basis it might be stated that in

This finding has also been reinforced by the literature review, (Suntharanurak, 2012) the basis of screening of rigging bids. Furthermore, this is also based on the research of (VisurthChorvichien et al. 2002). Based on the suggested recommendation (Suntharanurak, 2012), this study will use the difference between the Engineers’ Estimate and the winning bid price as a tool for screening collusive bidding.

It has been concluded that public procurement of sampled contracts with a difference between engineers’ estimate cost and a winning bid price less than 5 percent are assumed as collusive bids. Similarly, the bidder participation with only upto 3 bidders is defined as collusive bids. The researcher has used both suggested parameters for screening of collusive and non collusive bids in sampled bids in both cases.

Table 3 Comparison of Collusive and Non Collusive Bids

	Conventional Bidding		E-bidding	
	No.	%	No.	%
Non Collusive	24	53.00%	39	87.00%
Collusive	21	47.00%	6	13.00%
Total contracts	45	100%	45	100%

It is revealed from the analysis that collusive bids have proportion of 47% in conventional bidding system while it is only 13% in case of E-bidding system. This critical analysis is based on the two fundamental principle used for screening of collusive bids. As stated above, the limited number of bid participation with maximum of three and bid value with below 5% of Engineers’ Estimate has been set parameter for assessing the collusive screening of bids.

Macro Level Assessment of Bids

The literature review (**Antonio Estacheetal, 2012, policy research paper**) suggests the use of standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CV%) for research works for assessing the asymmetry of bids in public infrastructure projects. The researcher analysed the dispersion of bid values of bidders in each and every contract with the two highly acclaimed and user friendly tool of statistical analysis. The tool of standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CV) has been used for the real assessment of bid values. This reflects the overall dispersion of bid with the calculation of mean values. The calculation of each bid has been done with the same degree of methods adopted for the data of conventional bidding system and E-bidding. The equal degree of correction, if required, has been applied throughout the calculation. The Sample calculation of one bid has been presented in the following table.

Table 4. The Sample calculation of one bid has been presented

SN	Bid Values(x)	Mean Value(μ)	Deviation from Mean($x-\mu$)	Deviation from Mean($x-\mu$) ²	Standard Deviation(s)	CV %
1	19,981,785	26,967,521	-6,985,736	48,800,506,686,914	5,395,554	20.01
2	21,137,320		-5,830,202	33,991,249,933,416		
3	21,744,145		-5,223,377	27,283,668,794,160		
4	24,127,130		-2,840,391	8,067,823,331,016		
5	24,511,378		-2,456,144	6,032,643,714,925		
6	26,467,265		-500,257	250,257,280,705		
7	26,667,986		-299,536	89,721,734,149		
8	29,077,149		2,109,627	4,450,526,735,031		
9	34,025,168		7,057,646	49,810,370,808,284		
10	34,053,421		7,085,900	50,209,972,084,837		
11	34,849,992		7,882,470	62,133,337,012,827		
12	296,642,739		Total(S)	291,120,078,116,264		

Case I: the summary Assesment of bids on standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CV) of conventional bidding system has been presented here.

Table 5. The summary calculation of CV (%) of conventional bidding system

Lower limit	Upper limit	CV Range (Coefficient of Variation %)	No. of Contracts (f)
0	5	0-5	22
5	10	5-10	5
10	15	10-15	7
15	20	15-20	8
20	25	20-25	1
25	30	25-30	1
30	35	30-35	1
35	40	35-40	-
40	45	40-45	-
45	50	45-50	-
50	55	50-55	-
55	60	55-60	-
Total Bidders=			45

It is revealed from the table above that 22 (almost 50%) out of 45 bids has coefficient of variation in the range of (0-5) % and second most variability falls in the range of 15-20% and so is other ranges.

Case II: the summary assessment of bids on standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CV) of E- bidding system has been presented here.

Table 6 The summary calculation of CV (%) of E- bidding system

Lower limit	Upper limit	CV Range (Coefficient of Variation %)	No. of Contracts (f)
0	5	0-5	8
5	10	5-10	6
10	15	10-15	16
15	20	15-20	9
20	25	20-25	5
25	30	25-30	-
30	35	30-35	-
35	40	35-40	1
40	45	40-45	-
45	50	45-50	-
50	55	50-55	-
55	60	55-60	-
Total Bidders=			45

It is revealed from the table above that 16 (more than 33%) out of 45 bids has coefficient of variation in the range of (10-15) % and second most variability falls in the range of 15-20% and so is other ranges.

The comparative summary assessment of bids on standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CV) of sampled contract data of both bidding system has been presented here.

Table 7. The comparative summary calculation of CV (%)

CV Range (%)	Conventional bidding	E-bidding
0-5	22	8
5-10	5	6
10-15	7	16
15-20	8	9
20-25	1	5
25-30	1	0
30-35	1	0
35-40	0	1
40-45	0	0

45-50	0	0
50-55	0	0
55-60	0	0
Total =	45	45

The data presented in the table above also suggests the trend of collusive bidding in case of conventional bidding system.

The graphical presentation of dispersion and coefficient of variation has been presented below to reflect the real assessment of bids.

Figure 2. comparative summary of CV(%) in conventional bidding system and E-bidding

Trend of Responsive Bids and Percentage below Engineer's Estimate

The researcher tried to establish the trend of no. of responsive bids and percentage below Engineers' Estimate for winning bid of particular contract. To analyze relation between number of bidders and percentage below engineer's estimate, contract data of all the 45 bids in conventional bidding system and E-bidding system has been used. The bidding trend and correlation pattern of bids vs % below Engineers' Estimate has been worked out and presented in the graphical presentation.

Case I: All 45 contracts of conventional bidding system

Fig 3 Bidding Trend in conventional bidding system

It is revealed from the data reveals that there is strong correlation between these two variables. Simply it can be stated that, when the number of bidders increased, then percentage below engineer's estimate also increased. It can be stated that the factor of no. of bidders is 78% responsible for increment of low bids. The other associated and unknown factor for same is 22%.

Case II: All 45 contracts of E-bidding System

Fig 4 Bidding Trend in conventional bidding system

Bidding Trend in E-bidding System

It is revealed from the data that there is not strong correlation between no. of bidders and percentage below Engineers' Estimate. Simply it can be stated that, it's not necessarily when the number of bidders increased, then percentage below engineer's estimate also increased. It can be stated that the factor of no. of bidders is only 17% responsible for increment of low bids. The other associated and unknown factor for low bids is 83%.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are drawn;

- Collusive trending in conventional bidding system is reasonably high with 47% while the number sharply declines with 13% of the total sampled bid.
- It is revealed that 25% of winning bid is in the range of 0-5% below the Engineers' Estimate in conventional bidding system while it is only 13.85% in E-bidding.
- The ratio of bidders purchasing the bid documents and submission is considerably reduced after the launching of e-bidding system.
- The environment of construction business has been improved with consistent bidding pattern as revealed in the E-bidding system.
- Conventional ways of rate analysis uses the district rate and GoN Norms (DOR, DOLIDAR) which are based on labourintensive technology and this doesn't match with mechanized work system. Norms developed by concerning departments are not compatible with the desired specifications of clients.
- Foremost, the norms shall be designed and revised by the independent body under the constitution of Nepal. The implementing agency shouldn't have adopted the norms by themselves. This contradicts internationally accepted standard work culture for civil works contracting process.
- Further study for views of stakeholder need to be conducted for suggestive recommendations.

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References

- [1] Authority for the Supervision of Public Contracts, Department for the Co-ordination of European Union Policies , 2010. *The Comparative Survey on the National Public*

Procurement Systems across the PPN. Survey.

- [2] Bista, D. B., 2015. *Bidding Trend and Its Effects in Implementation on Road Projects of Division Road Offices*, Master Thesis. Changunarayan, Bhaktapur, Nepal: Nepal Engineering College.
- [3] Crowley, L.G. & Hancher, D.E., 1995. Risk Assessment of Competitive Procurement. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 121(2), pp.230-37.
- [4] CUTS International, 2008, n.d. *The Basics of Bid Rigging*. Briefing Paper No.10/2008. M.I. Road, Jaipur: Jaipur Printers Pvt. Ltd Centre for Competition, Investment & Economic Regulation (CUTS-C-CIER).
- [5] DoR, 2004. *Strategic Road Network*. SRN 2004. Kathmandu: Department of Roads.
- [6] DoR, 2007. *Sector Wide Road Programme and Priority Investment Plan*. Final Report. Babarmahal, Kathmandu, Nepal: Department of Roads Ministry of Physical Planning and Works, Government of Nepal.
- [7] DoR, 2012. *Statistics of Strategic Road Network 2011/12*. SSRN 2011/12. Babarmahal, Kathmandu: HMIS Unit, Department of Roads Ministry of Physical Planning, Works and Transport Management, Government of Nepal.
- [8] DoR, 2014. *SSRN 2013/14*. Statistics of Strategic Road Network. Babarmahal, Kathmandu: HMIS Unit, Department of Roads Ministry of Physical Infrastructure and Transport, Department of Roads.
- [9] Eastham, P.A. & Skitmore, M., 1993. *Construction Contractor's Project Selection: Decision Making within a Portfolio Framework*. In Proceedings International Seminar on Optimum Systems for Construction Management (ISOSCM '93), 1. Harbin, Heilongjiang, China, 1993.
- [10] Fair Trading Commission, Barbados, n.d. *Detecting, Mitigating & Fighting Bid Rigging in Public Procurement, Guidelines & Checklist*. Guidelines & Checklist. Good Hope, Green Hill, St. Michael, Barbados.
- [11] Farooqui, R.U., Saqib, M., Arif, F. & Lodi, S.H., 2008. An Assessment of General Trends Adopted for Bidding and Procurement in Construction Industry of Pakistan. In First International Conference on Construction In Developing Countries (ICCIDC-I), Advancing and Integrating Construction Education, Research & Practice. Karachi, Pakistan, 2008.
- [12] FCAN, 2012. *Federation of Contractor's Associations of Nepal (FCAN)*. [Online] Available at: HYPERLINK "<http://fcan.org.np/pages.php?pid=83>" <http://fcan.org.np/pages.php?pid=83> [Accessed 12 August 2015].
- [13] Group, I.E., n.d. *The World Bank and Public Procurement-An Independent Evaluation*. Appendixes to Volume II: Achieving Development Effectiveness Through Bank Procurement. IEG World Bank IFC MIGA.

- [14] Harris F and McCaffer,R , Modern Construction Management, 5th Edition, Blackwell Science
- [15] Mc Cormick, M., 2011. *MPCS-Project Management Solutions*. [Online] (1.5) Available at: HYPERLINK "www.cccormickpcs.com" www.cccormickpcs.com [Accessed 12 August 2015].
- [16] Mishra, A.K., and Singh, N.K., 2019. Bidders' Competitiveness in Rural Road Projects in Nepal: A Case Study of World Bank Funded Project, *Solid State Technology*, Volume: 62 Issue: 1, <http://www.solidstatetechnology.us/index.php/JSST/issue/view/9>
- [17] Porter, H.R. & Zona, J.D., 1992. *Detection of Bid Rigging in Procurement Auctions*. NBER Working Paper Series, Working Paper No. 4013. 1050 Massachusetts Avenue, Cambridge, MA 02138: National Bureau of Economic Research.
- [18] Suntharanurak, S., 2012. *Screening For Bid Rigging in Rural Road Procurement of Thailand*. Ph.D. Thesis. National Institute of Development Administration.
- [19] Zarkada-Fraser, A. & Skitmore, M.R., 1998. A Classification of Factors Influencing Participation in Collusive Tendering Agreement. In *Proceeding Theory Development and Models of Ethical Decision-Making track, Ethical and Sociteal Issues Conference*., 1998. American Marketing Association(AMA) Marketing Exchange Colloquium, Vienna Hilton, Austria